

Regional and International Mechanisms Influencing Alternative Dispute Resolution in Tanzania's Mining Sector

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Abstract:

This article examines how regional, international, and domestic legal frameworks shape Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) practices in Tanzania's mining sector. It situates ADR within Tanzania's legal system and assesses the extent to which instruments such as the East African Community (EAC) Treaty, the Southern African Development Community (SADC) Protocol on Finance and Investment, the International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID) Convention, the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL) Arbitration Rules, and the New York Convention influenced the use of ADR in the mining industry. The study further analyses how these instruments have influenced key national laws, including the Arbitration Act, the Tanzania Investment Act, and the Mining Act, all of which incorporate ADR mechanisms. The article finds that Tanzania has made progress in aligning domestic legislation with regional and international ADR standards but faces challenges in harmonization, institutional capacity, and enforcement.

Keywords: Alternative Dispute Resolution, Tanzania, UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules, Mining Act.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Tanzania's mining sector has witnessed significant foreign investment, leading to economic growth but also to an increase in disputes between investors and local communities. Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) mechanisms, including arbitration, mediation, and negotiation, have been employed to address these conflicts. The effectiveness of ADR in this context is influenced by regional and international legal frameworks that govern investment and dispute resolution. This article explores how instruments such as the East African Community (EAC) Treaty, the Southern African Development Community (SADC) Protocol on Finance and Investment, the International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID) Convention, and the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL) Arbitration Rules shape ADR practices in Tanzania's mining sector.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 The concept of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR)

Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) encompasses mechanisms such as negotiation, mediation, and arbitration, which provide parties with flexible, efficient, and less adversarial means of resolving disputes outside traditional court litigation. Negotiation is the most informal ADR method, relying on direct dialogue between parties to reach a mutually acceptable solution without third-party involvement.¹ Mediation involves a neutral third party who facilitates communication and helps disputing parties explore potential solutions, aiming for a voluntary settlement that preserves relationships.² Arbitration, in contrast, is a more formal process where a neutral arbitrator renders a binding decision, providing a mechanism akin to judicial adjudication but often faster and more flexible.³ Theoretically, ADR draws on principles from conflict resolution theory, which emphasizes understanding underlying interests rather than positions, and social exchange theory, which highlights the role of trust and perceived fairness in sustaining agreements.⁴

These theoretical frameworks suggest that ADR is effective because it promotes voluntary compliance, preserves relationships, reduces adversarial costs, and provides tailored solutions to complex disputes. In the context of investment disputes, ADR mechanisms are particularly valuable as they allow cross-border parties to resolve conflicts in a neutral

¹ Moore, C. W. (2014). *The mediation process: Practical strategies for resolving conflict* (4th ed.). Jossey-Bass.

² Bush, R. A. B., & Folger, J. P. (2005). *The promise of mediation: The transformative approach to conflict* (2nd ed.). Jossey-Bass.

³ Redfern, A., Hunter, M., Blackaby, N., & Partasides, C. (2015). *Law and practice of international commercial arbitration* (5th ed.). Sweet & Maxwell.

⁴ Deutsch, M. (1973). *The resolution of conflict: Constructive and destructive processes*. Yale University Press.

and predictable environment, accommodating differences in legal cultures, business practices, and expectations.

2.2 Legal basis for ADR in Investment Disputes

The legal basis for ADR in investment disputes is derived from both domestic legislation and international instruments. Domestically, Tanzania's Arbitration Act⁵ provides the statutory framework for arbitration, conciliation, and other forms of ADR, ensuring alignment with international standards such as the UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules.⁶ Internationally, Tanzania is a contracting party to the ICSID Convention (1966), the New York Convention (1958), and recognizes arbitration under UNCITRAL rules, all of which provide mechanisms for the resolution and enforcement of cross-border investment. These instruments collectively establish a framework that ensures neutrality, enforceability, and investor protection. ICSID provides facilities for conciliation and arbitration between states and foreign investors, while the New York Convention guarantees recognition and enforcement of foreign arbitral awards. The UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules, on the other hand, offer procedural guidance that harmonizes arbitration practices globally. Together, these domestic and international legal frameworks underpin the practical application of ADR in investment disputes, reinforcing Tanzania's commitment to providing a reliable and effective dispute resolution environment.

3. INTERNATIONAL INSTRUMENTS SHAPING ADR IN TAZANIA

3.1 International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID) Convention

Tanzania is a contracting member of the Convention on the Settlement of Investment Disputes between States and Nationals of Other States (ICSID Convention), established in 1966 under the World Bank. The Convention provides a neutral international forum for conciliation and arbitration of investment disputes between governments and investors from other contracting states.⁷ Its primary objective is to promote investor confidence and ensure impartial dispute resolution beyond domestic courts.

Awards rendered under ICSID are legally binding and enforceable in all 160 contracting states as though they were final judgments of national courts.⁸ This broad enforceability strengthens investor protection and promotes international investment stability. The

⁵ Arbitration Act, Cap. 15 R.E. 2020,

⁶ Mwakaje, J. (2021). The role of arbitration in promoting foreign investment in Tanzania. *African Journal of Law and Society*, 8(1), 89–103.

⁷ International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID). (1966). *Convention on the Settlement of Investment Disputes between States and Nationals of Other States*. Washington, D.C.: World Bank. Retrieved from <https://icsid.worldbank.org>. Accessed on 10 September 2024.

⁸ (ICSID, 1966, Art. 54).

Convention also encourages conciliation before arbitration, reflecting the principles of alternative dispute resolution (ADR) in promoting amicable settlements.⁹

However, Tanzania's experience with ICSID has been mixed. Several cases have ended unfavorably for the state, raising concerns about fairness and the perceived bias toward foreign investors. These outcomes have prompted debates over the balance between investor protection and national sovereignty.¹⁰ As a result, Tanzania has emphasized the need to strengthen domestic and regional ADR mechanisms to complement international frameworks and safeguard national interests.

3.2 UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules

The United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL) Arbitration Rules provide a comprehensive framework for the conduct of arbitration proceedings in international commercial and investment disputes. First adopted in 1976 and later revised in 2010 and 2013, these rules emphasize neutrality, fairness, and procedural flexibility, making them widely acceptable in both developed and developing jurisdictions.¹¹ They serve as a global standard that promotes efficiency and uniformity in arbitral proceedings while allowing parties autonomy in structuring their dispute resolution process.

In Tanzania, the principles of the UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules have been incorporated into the Arbitration Act,¹² which aligns domestic arbitration procedures with international best practices. This alignment enhances Tanzania's attractiveness as a venue for resolving both domestic and cross-border disputes, ensuring that arbitral proceedings meet globally recognized standards of impartiality and due process.¹³ The integration of UNCITRAL principles also reflects Tanzania's commitment to fostering confidence among foreign investors and promoting the use of alternative dispute resolution (ADR) in commercial and investment sectors.

Despite these developments, challenges remain in ensuring the consistent and effective application of the UNCITRAL framework. Limited institutional capacity, inadequate training among arbitration practitioners, and occasional judicial interference continue to hinder the smooth implementation of the Rules.¹⁴ Therefore, while Tanzania's legal framework is well aligned with international arbitration standards, further efforts are

⁹ Schreuer, C. H. (2009). *The ICSID Convention: A commentary* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.

¹⁰ Ndiho, D. (2017). Foreign investment and arbitration in Africa: A case study of Tanzania's experience with ICSID. *African Journal of International and Comparative Law*, 25(3), 421–436.

¹¹ United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL). (2013). *UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules* (as revised in 2013). United Nations. Retrieved from <https://uncitral.un.org>. Accessed on 7 August 2024.

¹² Arbitration Act, Cap. 15 R.E. 2020

¹³ Mwakaje, J. (2021). The role of arbitration in promoting foreign investment in Tanzania. *African Journal of Law and Society*, 8(1), 89–103.

¹⁴ Kileo, M. A. (2020). The practice and challenges of arbitration in Tanzania: A review of the Arbitration Act Cap. 15 R.E. 2020. *Eastern Africa Law Review*, 47(2), 112–128.

required to strengthen local institutions and enhance expertise to manage complex arbitration cases under the UNCITRAL framework effectively.

3. 3 New York Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards

The Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards (commonly known as the New York Convention) of 1958 provides a global framework for the enforcement of arbitral awards across signatory states. Tanzania, as a contracting state, is obligated to recognize and enforce foreign arbitration awards, ensuring that decisions rendered under international arbitration are respected domestically.¹⁵ This Convention enhances investor confidence by providing predictability and legal certainty, thereby encouraging cross-border trade and investment. While the Convention strengthens the enforceability of arbitration outcomes in Tanzania, challenges remain in its practical application. Local courts sometimes delay enforcement due to procedural inefficiencies or interpretive inconsistencies, which can undermine the Convention's objectives.¹⁶ Nonetheless, the New York Convention remains a cornerstone of international dispute resolution, complementing Tanzania's domestic arbitration framework and reinforcing the country's commitment to alternative dispute resolution mechanisms.

3.4. East African Community (EAC) Treaty

The East African Community (EAC) Treaty establishes a normative foundation for regional integration and cooperation among Partner States, including the harmonization of legal and judicial systems to promote effective dispute resolution. Although the Treaty does not expressly mandate the use of alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms, it provides a conducive legal and institutional framework that indirectly supports their application within the region.¹⁷ Article 5 of the Treaty outlines the EAC's objectives, emphasizing the development of policies and programs aimed at deepening cooperation across political, economic, social, and legal spheres. This integration facilitates a uniform legal environment conducive to investment and regional stability.

However, the EAC's influence in strengthening ADR remains limited due to several factors. Firstly, the harmonization directives are largely aspirational and depend heavily on the political will and domestic implementation capacity of individual Partner States. The Treaty's language, which requires Partner States to "take steps" towards harmonization, leaves considerable discretion in execution, resulting in uneven progress

¹⁵ United Nations. (1958). Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards (New York, 10 June 1958). United Nations Treaty Series, 330, 3–15. Retrieved from <https://uncitral.un.org>

¹⁶ Mwakaje, J. (2021). The role of arbitration in promoting foreign investment in Tanzania. *African Journal of Law and Society*, 8(1), 89–103.

¹⁷ East African Community Treaty (EAC), 1999, Art. 5).

across the region.¹⁸ Secondly, while the EACJ provides a regional forum for dispute adjudication, its jurisdiction and enforcement powers remain constrained by both the Treaty and subsequent protocols, thereby limiting its ability to supervise or enforce uniform ADR mechanisms.¹⁹

Moreover, the existence of divergent national legal frameworks, resource disparities, and policy priorities among Partner States contributes to fragmented ADR practices in the region. These challenges indicate that while the EAC Treaty offers an institutional and normative basis for harmonized dispute resolution, its implementation and impact on ADR remain partial and dependent on Member States' commitment to regional legal integration. Thus, the EAC framework provides an important legal and policy foundation for ADR in East Africa, but practical effectiveness requires stronger enforcement mechanisms, consistent national reforms, and enhanced regional cooperation.

3.5 Southern African Development Community (SADC) Protocol on Finance and Investment

The Southern African Development Community (SADC) Protocol on Finance and Investment (FIP), adopted in 2006, aims to harmonize financial and investment policies among member states to promote sustainable economic growth and regional integration. It establishes a framework to create an enabling environment that encourages both intra-regional and international investment by fostering transparency, stability, and predictability in the financial and investment sectors.²⁰ The Protocol underscores the importance of cooperation in areas such as investment, taxation, and financial markets as part of broader economic governance within the SADC region.

Article 9 of the Protocol specifically promotes the use of alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms for settling investment disputes. It calls upon member states to establish and maintain effective systems for the peaceful resolution of disputes arising from investment activities through negotiation, mediation, conciliation, or arbitration.²¹ By emphasizing ADR, the Protocol reflects SADC's commitment to ensuring investor protection, minimizing conflicts, and upholding the rule of law in regional economic relations.²² These mechanisms are intended to provide efficient and impartial platforms for resolving disputes without undermining investor confidence or disrupting economic activity.

¹⁸ Döveling, J. (2018). Harmonisation of Laws in the East African Community. TGCL Series. University of Dar es Salaam School of Law.

¹⁹ Tralac. (2018, October 1). Dispute settlement in the East African Community (EAC). Trade Law Centre (tralac). Retrieved from <https://www.tralac.org>. Accessed on 6 July 2025.

²⁰ Southern African Development Community (SADC). (2006). Protocol on Finance and Investment. Gaborone, Botswana. Retrieved from <https://www.sadc.int>. Accessed on 1 October 2024.

²¹ (SADC, 2006, Art. 9).

²² Tralac. (2020, February 18). The SADC Protocol on Finance and Investment: Challenges and opportunities for investment dispute resolution. Trade Law Centre (tralac). Retrieved from <https://www.tralac.org> accessed on 4 March 2024.

Despite these provisions, the implementation of the Protocol remains inconsistent across member states, including Tanzania. Although Tanzania is a signatory, the alignment of its domestic legal framework with regional ADR standards has been limited, weakening the effectiveness of the Protocol in practice.²³ The suspension of the SADC Tribunal in 2010 further reduced the region's capacity to enforce or supervise investment-related dispute resolution.²⁴ Consequently, while the SADC Protocol provides a strong regional legal foundation for ADR, its effectiveness depends largely on national implementation and the restoration of robust regional dispute resolution mechanisms.

4. INTERACTION BETWEEN REGIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL MECHANISMS

The interaction between regional and international alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms in Tanzania's mining sector reflects both complementarity and tensions. Regional instruments, such as the SADC Protocol on Finance and Investment, seek to harmonize investment policies among member states and promote the use of ADR in resolving disputes.²⁵ These frameworks provide guidance on negotiation, mediation, and arbitration while encouraging consistency and predictability in regional investment dispute settlement. In practice, however, their impact is sometimes constrained by domestic laws that emphasize state sovereignty and national regulatory prerogatives over full adherence to regional commitments.

International mechanisms, including the ICSID Convention and UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules, offer robust, neutral, and globally recognized frameworks for dispute resolution, enhancing investor confidence and providing enforceable outcomes across jurisdictions International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes.²⁶ Nevertheless, tensions arise when international ADR processes conflict with Tanzanian domestic laws, especially in sensitive sectors such as mining and natural resources, where the state maintains regulatory authority over investment and exploitation rights. These interactions highlight the need for coherent policy alignment and institutional capacity to ensure that regional and international mechanisms complement rather than undermine domestic legal frameworks. Strengthening coordination between these mechanisms can enhance the effectiveness of ADR, promote investor protection, and safeguard national interests in Tanzania's mining sector.

²³ Chigara, B., & Magwape, M. (2017). *Southern African Development Community (SADC) law: Investment protection and the rule of law*. Routledge.

²⁴ Nathan, L. (2011). Solidarity triumphs over democracy: The dissolution of the SADC Tribunal. *Development Dialogue*, 57(1), 139–153.

²⁵ Southern African Development Community (SADC). (2006). *Protocol on Finance and Investment*. Gaborone, Botswana. Retrieved from <https://www.sadc.int>. Accessed on 6 June 2024.

²⁶ International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID). (1966). *Convention on the Settlement of Investment Disputes between States and Nationals of Other States*. Washington, D.C.: World Bank. Retrieved from <https://icsid.worldbank.org>. Accessed on 5 August 2024.

5. DOMESTIC LEGAL STATUS OF INTERNATIONAL AND REGIONAL INSTRUMENTS

Tanzania operates under a dualist legal system, meaning that international and regional instruments do not automatically have legal effect unless incorporated into domestic law through legislation.²⁷ While the country is a signatory to several regional and global frameworks that support alternative dispute resolution (ADR) including the East African Community (EAC) Treaty, the Southern African Development Community (SADC) Protocol on Finance and Investment, the International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID) Convention, the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL) Arbitration Rules, and the New York Convention of 1958 their provisions are only applicable within Tanzania to the extent that they have been domesticated.²⁸ In practice, Tanzania has achieved this domestication both explicitly and implicitly through legislative reforms that align national law with international ADR standards.

A key example is the Arbitration Act,²⁹ which modernized Tanzania's arbitration framework and adopted principles from the UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Arbitration. The Act guarantees party autonomy, enforces arbitral awards, and limits judicial interference, reflecting the country's commitment to global arbitration norms. Similarly, the Tanzania Investment Act,³⁰ establishes the Tanzania Investment Centre (TIC) and provides for conciliation and arbitration in investment disputes between the government and investors. Section 33(2) of the Act³¹ expressly allows parties to resolve disputes under the rules of recognized international institutions, such as ICSID or UNCITRAL, demonstrating Tanzania's adherence to its international obligations.³² The Mining Act,³³ together with the Mining (Dispute Resolution) Rules, 2021, further illustrates this domestication. Section 150 of the Act³⁴ empowers the Mining Commission to facilitate amicable settlement through mediation and arbitration before parties' resort to litigation, thereby embedding ADR into the regulatory framework for the mining industry.³⁵

²⁷ See *Attorney General v. Rev. Christopher Mtikila* [1995] TLR 31 (CA), confirming Tanzania's dualist approach to international law.

²⁸ United Nations, Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards (New York, 1958); Southern African Development Community (SADC), Protocol on Finance and Investment (2006); East African Community (EAC), Treaty for the Establishment of the East African Community (1999).

²⁹ Cap. 15 [R.E. 2023].

³⁰ Cap 38 R.E 2023.

³¹ Tanzania Investment Act Cap 38 R.E 2023.

³² United Nations, Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards (New York, 1958); Southern African Development Community (SADC), Protocol on Finance and Investment (2006); East African Community (EAC), Treaty for the Establishment of the East African Community (1999).

³³ Cap. 123 [R.E. 2023].

³⁴ The Mining Act Cap 123 R.E 2023.

³⁵ The Mining Act, Cap. 123 [R.E. 2019], s. 105; Mining (Dispute Resolution) Rules, GN No. 438 of 2021.

Collectively, these statutes show that Tanzania has progressively internalized the norms and principles of regional and international ADR instruments. Although not all treaties are directly enforceable without enabling legislation, the country's legislative framework demonstrates a deliberate effort to align domestic law with global best practices. These reforms signify Tanzania's broader policy shift toward providing investors and local stakeholders with structured, transparent, and non-adversarial mechanisms for dispute resolution, particularly in the mining sector, where complex disputes are frequent and often involve cross-border parties.

6. INFLUENCE OF INTERNATIONAL AND REGIONAL ADR FRAMEWORKS ON TANZANIA'S MINING LEGISLATION

Regional and international ADR frameworks have significantly influenced Tanzania's mining legislation and institutional approaches to dispute resolution. The ICSID Convention has been particularly influential, as Tanzania's recognition of investor-state arbitration through ICSID is reflected in both the Tanzania Investment Act and the Mining Act, which allow foreign investors to submit disputes to international arbitration.³⁶ This alignment ensures conformity with global standards of investment protection and fosters confidence among investors that disputes can be resolved impartially and efficiently. The UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules and the New York Convention have also left a clear imprint on the Tanzanian arbitration regime. The Arbitration Act incorporates UNCITRAL principles that emphasize neutrality, procedural fairness, and party autonomy. At the same time, the New York Convention guarantees the recognition and enforcement of foreign arbitral awards, enhancing legal certainty for investors in the mining industry.³⁷

Furthermore, regional instruments such as the SADC Protocol on Finance and Investment and the East African Commission Treaty have guided Tanzania's adoption of ADR mechanisms by promoting the harmonization of dispute resolution standards across member states. The introduction of the Mining (Dispute Resolution) Rules, 2021, and the emphasis on mediation and arbitration before litigation reflect these regional influences.³⁸ The rules demonstrate Tanzania's commitment to early, amicable settlement of disputes in line with SADC's objectives of promoting regional stability and economic integration. Similarly, the EAC's framework for legal harmonization and cooperation has encouraged Tanzania to modernize its laws and strengthen institutional

³⁶ International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID), Convention on the Settlement of Investment Disputes between States and Nationals of Other States (1966); Tanzania Investment Act, s. 33(2).

³⁷ The Arbitration Act, Cap. 15 [R.E. 2020]; United Nations, UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules (as revised in 2013); Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards (New York, 1958).

³⁸ Southern African Development Community (SADC), Protocol on Finance and Investment, art. 9 (2006).

capacity for ADR in sectors of strategic importance, including mining.³⁹ Overall, Tanzania's mining dispute resolution regime has evolved into a hybrid system that combines domestic legislative reforms with obligations derived from regional and international frameworks. This synthesis ensures that ADR mechanisms are both locally grounded and globally credible. Nevertheless, gaps remain in terms of full implementation and enforcement, particularly regarding institutional capacity and technical expertise in managing complex mining disputes. Addressing these challenges will be essential to ensuring that the influence of international and regional frameworks translates into practical effectiveness and equitable outcomes within Tanzania's mining sector.

7. CHALLENGES IN HARMONIZATION AND ENFORCEMENT

The effective harmonization and enforcement of alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms in Tanzania's mining sector face several significant challenges, which are compounded by real-world disputes and legal inconsistencies. Conflicts between national laws and international commitments create uncertainty and hinder the application of ADR mechanisms. For instance, while Tanzania is a contracting state to the ICSID Convention, which provides facilities for conciliation and arbitration of investment disputes, several cases have resulted in unfavorable outcomes for the state. In one notable instance, a Canadian mining company reported that Tanzania agreed to pay US\$27 million to settle an ICSID case over the revocation of mining licences, marking the third such settlement the state has reached with investors who held those permits. This situation underscores the tension between domestic legal frameworks and international obligations, affecting the effectiveness of ADR in the mining sector.⁴⁰

Limited expertise and resources within national institutions affect the quality and efficiency of ADR processes. The Tanzanian government has issued new Mining (Dispute Resolution) Rules to regulate disputes in the sector, aiming to promote Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) while placing public interest at the centre of the mining economy. However, the implementation of these rules has been inconsistent, and the capacity of institutions to handle complex mining disputes remains a significant challenge. Lack of awareness among local communities about ADR options and procedures limits their ability to participate effectively in dispute resolution. Disputes related to tax, regulatory compliance, labour, finance, and investment are prevalent in Tanzania's mining sector. However, the involvement of local communities in these disputes is often limited due to insufficient awareness and understanding of ADR mechanisms.

³⁹ East African Community (EAC), Treaty for the Establishment of the East African Community, Arts. 5 and 126 (1999).

⁴⁰ Global Arbitration Review. (2024, November 21). Tanzania settles third mining case.

8. CONCLUSION

Regional and international mechanisms are pivotal in shaping alternative dispute resolution (ADR) practices in Tanzania's mining sector. These frameworks provide structured, neutral, and internationally recognized tools for resolving investment and commercial disputes, contributing to predictability and investor confidence. However, their effectiveness largely depends on the harmonization of national laws with regional and international instruments, the capacity of institutions to manage complex disputes, and sustained political support. Addressing the challenges identified including legal inconsistencies, limited institutional capacity, low public awareness, and variable political commitment while implementing targeted reforms, capacity-building programs, and awareness initiatives, can significantly enhance the effectiveness of ADR in the mining sector. Strengthening these mechanisms will promote fair, efficient, and sustainable dispute resolution, ultimately support equitable outcomes and foster a more stable and attractive environment for investment in Tanzania's mining industry.